

Primer sets for DNA barcoding of plant pathogenic fungi

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Abstract

This article outlines the primer sets used for polymerase chain reaction for DNA barcoding of plant pathogenic fungi. The key gene targets/loci for fungi are the partial internal transcribed spacer (ITS), β -tubulin (BenA/Tub2), Calmodulin (CAM or CAL), RNA polymerase II subunit 1 (RPB1) and 2 (RPB2), actin (ACT), Translation elongation factor 1-alpha (tef1), mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase I (COI) and II (CO2), Chitin synthase (CHS-1), Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH), Glutamine synthetase (GS), Manganese-superoxide dismutase (SOD2), histone (his3), Intergenic sequence between Apn2 DNA lyase and Mat1-2-1 (ApMAT), partial apurinic DNA lyase gene (APN2), partial mating-type locus gene (MAT1-2) genes and the Ras-related protein gene (Ypt1) genes.

Keywords: polymerase chain reaction, partial internal transcribed spacer, β -tubulin, Translation elongation factor 1-alpha

Table 1 lists the primer sets used in polymerase chain reaction (PCR) assays for DNA barcoding of plant pathogenic fungi. The key gene targets/loci for fungi are the internal transcribed spacer (ITS), β -tubulin (BenA/Tub2), Calmodulin (CAM or CAL), RNA polymerase II subunit 1 (RPB1) and 2 (RPB2), actin (ACT), Translation elongation factor 1-alpha (tef1), mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase I (COI) and II (CO2), Chitin synthase (CHS-1), Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH), Glutamine synthetase (GS), Manganese-superoxide dismutase (SOD2), histone (his3), Intergenic sequence between Apn2 DNA lyase and Mat1-2-1 (ApMAT), partial apurinic DNA lyase gene (APN2), partial mating-type locus gene (MAT1-2) genes and the Ras-related protein gene (Ypt1) genes. Key references are provided for fungal group DNA barcodes, PCR assay cocktail preparation, and cycling conditions. These primer sets have been used or are currently used by mycologists, plant pathologists, and researchers from specific organizations (such as those in the plant quarantine services). Readers are still advised to check the correctness (for updates) of these sequences in the relevant reference.

Table 1. Primer sets in PCR assays for DNA barcoding of plant pathogenic fungi.

Target/Locus	Primer Name	Direction	Sequence	Reference
Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS)	ITS1	Forward	TCC GTA GGT GAA CCT GCG G	White et al. (1990)
	ITS4	Reverse	TCC TCC GCT TAT TGA TAT GC	Glass and Donaldson (1995)
β -tubulin (BenA/Tub2)	Bt2a	Forward	GGT AAC CAA ATC GGT GCT GCT TTC	Glass and Donaldson (1995)
	Bt2b	Reverse	ACC CTC AGT GTA GTG ACC CTT GGC	Glass and Donaldson (1995)
	T1	Forward	AAC ATG CGT GAG ATT GTA AGT	O'Donnell and Cigelnik E (1997)
	T2	Reverse	TAG TGA CCC TTG GCC CAGT TG	O'Donnell and Cigelnik E (1997)
	Btub2Fd	Forward	GTB CAC CTY CAR ACC GGY CAR TG	Woudenberg et al. (2009)
	Btub4Rd	Reverse	CCR GAY TGR CCR AAR ACR AAG TTG TC	Woudenberg et al. (2009)
	Bsens	Forward	ATC ACW CAC TCI CTI GGT GGT GG	Lesage-Meessen et al (2011)
	Brev	Reverse	CAT GAA GAA RTG IAG ACG IGG G	Lesage-Meessen et al (2011)

Calmodulin (CaM)	CMD5	Forward	CCG AGT ACA AGG ARG CCT TC	Hong et al. (2006)
	CMD6	Reverse	CCG ATR GAG GTC ATR ACG TGG	Hong et al. (2006)
	CF1	Forward	GCC GAC TCT TTG ACY GAR GAR	Peterson et al. (2005)
	CF4	Reverse	TTT YTG CAT CAT RAG YTG GAC	Peterson et al. (2005)
	CAL-228F	Forward	GAG TTC AAG GAG GCC TTC TCC C	Carbone and Kohn (1999)
	CAL-737R	Reverse	CAT CTT TCT GGC CAT CAT GG	Carbone and Kohn (1999)
	CL1C	Forward	GAA TTC AAG GAG GCC TTC TC	Weir et al. (2012)
	CL2C	Reverse	CTT CTG CAT CAT GAG CTG GAC	Weir et al. (2012)
	CL1	Forward	GAR TWC AAG GAG GCC TTC TC	O'Donnell et al (2000)
	CL2A	Reverse	TTT TTG CAT CAT GAG TTG GAC	O'Donnell et al (2000)
RNA polymerase II subunit 2 (RPB2)	RPB2-5f	Forward	GAY GAY MGW GAT CAY TTY GG	Liu et al (1999)
	RPB2-7cR	Reverse	CCC ATR GCT TGY TTR CCC AT	Liu et al (1999)
	5Feur	Forward	GAY GAY CGK GAY CAY TTC GG	Houbraken et al (2012)
	7CReur	Reverse	CCC ATR GCY TGY TTR CCC AT	Houbraken et al (2012)
Large Subunit (LSU, 28S) of the rRNA	LROR	Forward	ACC CGC TGA ACT TAA GC	Vilgalys and Hester (1990)
	LR5	Reverse	TCC TGA GGG AAA CTT CG	Vilgalys and Hester (1990)
Actin (ACT)	ACT512f	Forward	ATG TGC AAG GCC GGT TTC G	Carbone and Kohn (1999)
	ACT783r	Reverse	TAC GAG TCC TTC TGG CCC AT	Carbone and Kohn (1999)
	CA5R	Forward	GTG AAC AAT GGA TGG ACC AGA TTC GTC G	Daniel et al. (2001)
	CA14	Reverse	AAC TGG GAT GAC ATG GAG AAG ATC TGG C	Daniel et al. (2001)
Translation Elongation Factor 1-alpha (TEF1 α)	EF1-983F	Forward	GCY CCY GGH CAY CGT GAY TTY AT	Rehner and Buckley (2005)
	EF1-1567R	Reverse	ACH GTR CCR ATA CCA CCR ATC TT	Rehner and Buckley (2005)
	EF1-2218R	Reverse	AT GAC ACC RAC RGC RAC RGT YTG	Rehner and Buckley (2005)
	EF1-1018F	Forward	GAY TTC ATC AAG AAC ATG AT	Stielow et al (2015)
	EF1-1620R	Reverse	GAC GTT GAA DCC RAC RTT GTC	Stielow et al (2015)
	EF1-728F	Forward	CAT CGA GAA GTT CGA GAA GG	Carbone and Kohn (1999)
	TEF1LLErev	Reverse	AAC TTG CAG GCA ATG TGG	Carbone and Kohn (1999)
	ef1	Forward	ATG GGT AAG GA(A/G) GAC AAG AC	Geiser et al. (2004)
	ef2	Reverse	GGA (G/A)GT ACC AGT (G/C)AT CAT GTT	Geiser et al. (2004)
RNA polymerase II subunit 1 (RPB1)	RPB1af	Forward	GAR TGY CCD GGD CAY TTY GG	Stiller et al. (1997)
	RPB1cr	Reverse	CCN GCD ATN TCR TTR TCC ATR TA	Stiller et al. (1997)
Small Subunit (SSU, 18S) of the rRNA	NS1	Forward	GTA GTC ATA TGC TTG TCT C	White et al. (1990)
	NS4	Reverse	CTT CCG TCA ATT CCT TTA AG	White et al. (1990)
mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase I (COI) gene	OomCoxI-Levup	Forward	TCA WCW MGA TGG CTT TTT TCA AC	Robideau et al. (2011)
	OomCoxI-Levlo	Reverse	CYT CHG GRT GWC CRA AAA ACC AAA	Robideau et al. (2011)
mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase 2 (CO2) gene	FM75	Forward	CCT TGG CAA TTA GGA TTT CAA GAT	Martin et al. (2003)
	FM78	Reverse	ACA AAT TTC ACT ACA TTG TCC	Martin et al. (2003)
Chitin synthase (CHS-1)	CHS-79F	Forward	TGG GGC AAG GAT GCT TGG AAG AAG	Carbone and Kohn (1999)
	CHS-345R	Reverse	TGG AAG AAC CAT CTG TGA GAG TTG	Carbone and Kohn (1999)
	GDF	Forward	GCC GTC AAC GAC CCC TTC ATT GA	Templeton et al. (1992)

Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH)	GDR	Reverse	GGG TGG AGT CGT ACT TGA GCA TGT	Templeton et al. (1992)
Glutamine synthetase (GS)	GSF1	Forward	ATG GCC GAG TAC ATC TGG	Stephenson et al. (1997)
	GSF3	Reverse	GCC GGT GGA GGA ACC GTC G	Weir et al. (2012)
	GSR1	Forward	GAA CCG TCG AAG TTC CAG	Stephenson et al. (1997)
	GSR2	Reverse	GAA CCG TCG AAG TTC CAC	Weir et al. (2012)
Manganese-superoxide dismutase (SOD2)	SODglo2-F	Forward	CAG ATC ATG GAG CTG CAC CA	Moriwaki et al. (2009)
	SODglo2-R	Reverse	TAG TAC GCG TGC TCG GAC AT	Moriwaki et al. (2009)
Histone (his3)	CYLH3F	Forward	AGG TCC ACT GGT GGC AAG	Crous et al. (2004)
	CYLH3R	Reverse	AGC TGG ATG TCC TTG GAC TG-3	Crous et al. (2004)
Intergenic sequence between Apn2 DNA lyase and Mat1-2-1 (ApMAT)	APF-long	Forward	TCA TTC TAC GTA TGT GCC CGC CCG TTG	Silva et al. (2012)
	APR-long	Reverse	CCA GAA ATA CAC CGA ACT TGC AAA GAT	Silva et al. (2012)
Partial apurinic DNA lyase gene (APN2)	Apn1W1F	Forward	ATG GAG CAC AAA AAC GAA CA	Crouch et al. (2009)
	Apn1W1R	Reverse	GCG GAG CAG AGG ATG TAG TC	Crouch et al. (2009)
Partial mating type locus gene (MAT1-2)	Mat1M72F	Forward	ACG GCA AAC GGC TCA GGG AGT G	Crouch et al. (2009)
	Mat1M72R	Reverse	AAT GCC GAG TCC CAC GAG GTT CG	Crouch et al. (2009)
Ras-related protein gene (Ypt1)	Ypt1F	Forward	CGA CCA TYG GYG TKG ACT TT	Chen et al. (1996)
	Ypt5R	Reverse	GCA GCT TGT TSA CGT TCT CR	Chen et al. (1996)

References and Further Readings

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